

AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF VATAJA PRATISHYAYA (ALLERGIC RHINITIS) IN CHILDREN: A CASE REPORT

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Article Received on
23 August 2025,

Revised on 12 Sept. 2025,
Accepted on 02 Oct. 2025

DOI: 10.20959/wjpr202519-38471

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2. ABSTRACT

Introduction: According to *Ayurveda*, *Nasa* is the gateway to *Shirah*. *Acharya Sushruta* and *Acharya Vagbhata*, respectively, have described 31 and 18 *Nasa roga*. There is a correlation between Allergic Rhinitis and *Vataja Pratishyaya*. Numerous therapeutic approaches, including *Gritapana*, *Nasya*, *Dhumapana*, *Swedana*, and internal medicine, can be used to control *Vataja Pratishyaya*. **Material and Methods:** The patient came to *Kaumarbhritya* (Paediatric) OPD with symptoms of Excessive nasal discharge (Rhinorrhoea), Excessive sneezing, Nasal dryness, itching in nasal cavity from 15 days. It was thoroughly examined, and therapies such as *pathadi tail Nasya* were suggested. **Result:** The disease *Vataja Pratishyaya* completely resolved after 28 days of the *Ayurvedic* treatment. **Discussion:** The majority of rhinitis symptoms are similar to those of *vata-kaphaj pratishaya*. Due to their *Vata-Kaphaja* nature and anti-inflammatory and antiallergic properties, *Nasya* and *Abhyantara yoga* have demonstrated notable improvement.

3. KEYWORDS: *Vataja Pratishyaya*, Allergic Rhinitis, Rhinorrhoea, *Nasya*, *Pathadi tail*.

4. INTRODUCTION

In India, 22% of people have allergic rhinitis.^[1] An allergic irritation of the nasal membrane is known as allergic rhinitis. It happens when someone inhales an allergen, such as dust,

pollen, or animal dander. Allergic rhinitis is characterized by rhinorrhoea, sneezing, itching, nasal congestion, and blockage.^[2] Each person is exposed to a variety of chemical and biological substances found in their surroundings on a daily basis. While some of these substances, such as food and medications, are beneficial to the body, others, such as microorganisms, are typically detrimental. A response to an irritant causes rhinitis, an inflammation of the mucous membrane (the moist lining of the nose), which can result in clogged noses, sneezing fits, or nasal discharge. Soreness might also result from too much mucus dripping into the neck. If left untreated, allergic rhinitis can result in atopic eczema, sinusitis, nasal polyps, otitis media, and Eustachian tube dysfunction. The illness affects children's physical, social, and psychological well-being in addition to their academic performance. Allergy is defined as an aberrant response of bodily tissues to certain foreign compounds, known as allergens, which are often pretentious in nature. The body creates a particular antibody in reaction to allergens. IgE is the immunoglobulin that is essential in allergic rhinitis.

The current medical system recommends corticosteroids, decongestants, and antihistamines. In terms of Ayurveda, it is linked to *Vataja Prathishyaya*. Certain beliefs suggest that *Vata* and *Kapha* are the two primary *Doshas* that lead to the emergence of this illness. The symptoms of allergic rhinitis and *Vataja Prathishyaya* are same. This common sickness is characterized by *Anaddha Pihita Nasa*, *Tanusrava*, *Shosha* in *Gala Taalu* and *Oshta*, and discomfort in *Shankapradesha*. The treatment strategies employed in this case study include internal medicine, which has a *Rasayana* effect and helps prevent the problem from returning, and *Nasya*, which helps restore the nasal mucosa to normal.

5. MATERIALS AND METHODS

OBJECTIVE: To assess the role of *Pathadi tail Nasya* in the treatment of *Vataja pratishayaya* (Allergic Rhinitis).

CASE REPORT

10 years old female child come to *Kaumarbhritya* (Paediatric) OPD at Dr. D.Y. Patil college of *Ayurved* and Research Center, Pimpri, Pune with the chief complaints of Excessive nasal discharge (Rhinorrhoea), Excessive sneezing (>18 times in a Morning and >12 times in Night), Nasal obstruction, itching in nasal cavity from 15 days and after symptomatic review she was diagnosed as *Vataja pratishayaya*. She went to a new place, which was dusty and caused some changes in the climate. The patient has since displayed the previously

mentioned symptoms. The patient has had the same symptom for the past two years. In order to control the illness, the patient took cetirizine suspension in the evening, but they did not get adequate alleviation. Thus, the patient has arrived at *Kaumarbhritya* (Paediatric) OPD in order to receive *Ayurvedic* treatment for their allergic rhinitis.

History of Present Illness

Patient was taking allopathic medications before coming to our hospital but she was not satisfied.

History of Past Illness

Patients have no systemic illness.

Family History

No significant history related to disease was found.

Astavidha Pareeksha

1. *Nadi* – 90/min, 2. *Shabda* – *Spastha*, 3. *Mala* – *Saama*, 4. *Sparsha* – *Prakruit*, 5. *Mutra*—*Prakrut*, 6. *Druk* – *Prakrut*, 7. *Jivha* – *Alipta*, 8. *Akruti* – *Madhyam*.

Personal history

1. Diet mixed, 2. Sleep – Disturbed due to nasal congestion, 3. Micturition – 5-6 times/day
Appetite – Adequate, 4. Bowel – Incomplete evacuation.

Samprapti Ghatak

1. *Dosha* – *Vata and kapha*, 2. *Srotodusti* – *Sanga*, 3. *Dushaya* – *Rasa*, 4. *UdbhavaSthana* – *Aamashya*, 5. *Agni* – *Manda*, 6. *VyaktaSthana* – *Nasa Avastha Aam*, 7. *Sanchayasthana* – *Nasa, gala*.

5.9 *Dasavidha pariksha*

(1) *prakriti*: (a) *sharirika*—*Vataja* (b) *mansika*—*satvika*.

(2) *vikriti*: (a) *dosha*—*tridoshaja* (b) *dushya*—*rakta, mamsa, meda*, (c) *adhishthana*—*twak*
(d) *srotodushti*—*vimarga-gamana*.

(3) *sara* — *mansa*.

(4) *samhanana*—*Pravara*.

(5) *pramana*—*Pravara*.

(6) *satmya*—*Madhura*.

(7) *satva—Pravara.*

(8) *aharashakti—avara.*

(9) *vyayam shakti—avara.*

(10) *vaya—balyavastha.*

Nose and PNS Examination

Anterior Rhinoscopy – Nasal Mucosa – Pale.

Inferior Turbinate Hypertrophy (ITH) – Bilateral.

Nasal Endoscopy - Nasal Mucosa – Pale.

Inferior Turbinate Hypertrophy (ITH) – Bilateral.

Throat Examination – Tonsils – within normal limit.

Posterior Pharyngeal wall – Congestion.

PNS Tenderness – Negative (-ve).

Eye Examination - within normal limit.

LINE OF TREATMENT

Time Line: 6/11/2024 to 3/12/2024

Table no. 1: Intervention.

Sr. No.	Duration	Ausadhi
1	First Week	1. <i>sthanik(shirogata) snehan</i> with <i>Tila Taila</i> 2. <i>sthanik(Shirogata) swedana</i> with plan Hot water 3. <i>Pathadi Taila Nasya</i> – 4 ⁰ - 4 ⁰ at morning.
2	Second week	1. <i>sthanik(shirogata) snehan</i> with <i>Tila Taila</i> 2. <i>sthanik(Shirogata) swedana</i> with plan Hot water 3. <i>Pathadi Taila Nasya</i> – 4 ⁰ - 4 ⁰ at morning.
3	Third week	1. <i>sthanik(shirogata) snehan</i> with <i>Tila Taila</i> 2. <i>sthanik(Shirogata) swedana</i> with plan Hot water 3. <i>Pathadi Taila Nasya</i> – 4 ⁰ - 4 ⁰ at morning.
4	Fourth week	1. <i>sthanik(shirogata) snehan</i> with <i>Tila Taila</i> 2. <i>sthanik(Shirogata) swedana</i> with plan Hot water 3. <i>Pathadi Taila Nasya</i> – 4 ⁰ - 4 ⁰ at morning.

ADVICE PATHYA

The patient was discouraged from drinking cold water, sleeping with the head down in a prone position (*Adhomukha Shayana*), sleeping during the day (*Divaswapna*), and consuming hard-to-digest foods (*Guru Ahara*) that block bodily channels (*Abhishyandi*), such as curd (*Dadhi*), milk (*Ksheera*), black gram (*Masha*), and dry and hard foods (*Ruksha, Katina Anna*) like *Bhakri*. It is advised that the patient wear a mask outside and to drink warm water.

Table No. 2: Assessment Criteria.^[4]

Total Nasal Symptom Score		
Symptoms	Assessment	Scale
1. Nasal discharge	No Discharge.	0
	Negligible Discharge.	1
	Continuous Discharge.	2
	Profuse Discharge.	3
2. Sneezing	No.	0
	1-5 Bouts per day.	1
	6-10 Bouts per day.	2
	11-20 Bouts per day.	3
	More than 20 Bouts per day.	4
3. Nasal Obstruction	No Obstruction.	0
	Partial Occasional and unilateral.	1
	Partial Occasional and bilateral.	2
	Complete, Frequently and Unilateral.	3
	Always complete and Bilateral.	4
4. Itching in Nasal Cavity	No symptoms.	0
	Mild Awareness but not troubled.	1
	Troublesome but not interfering with normal daily activities or sleep.	2
	Interfering with normal daily activities or sleep.	3

6. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Sr. No.	Symptoms	Day 0	1 st week	2 nd week	3 rd week	4 th week
1	Nasal discharge	2	1	0	0	0
2	Sneezing	3	3	2	0	0
3	Nasal Obstruction	4	3	1	0	0
4	Itching in Nasal Cavity	2	2	1	1	0

When the patient arrived to the *Kaumarbhritya* (Paediatric) OPD, the patient had moderate-grade nasal itching, nasal discharge and severe-grade nasal obstruction and sneezing. Congestion was seen in the posterior pharyngeal wall, and bilateral inferior turbinate hypertrophy was seen. Signs and symptoms improved every week as a result of the *Nasaya Karma* approach. The signs and symptoms completely disappeared after four weeks of *Pathadi taila Nasaya Karma*.

DISCUSSION

Snehana karma before *Nasya* very effective to *sthanasansharay* of *Vyadhi* and also *vatashamak* property. As to the classical *Ayurvedic* scripture, *Swedana* has the ability to calm *Sthambha*, *Gourava*, and *Sita*. Its qualities include *Vata-Kapha samana*.^[5] It facilitates simple secretion evacuation and cleanses the *srotas*. *Pathadi Taila* has *Katu, tikta rasa, ushna veerya*

and *laghurookshna*, *teekshnaguna*. This medication is on their premises. reduces *doshas* by alleviating the disease's symptoms. *Pathadi Taila*^[6] is possessing the qualities of *vatakaphahara*, *snehana*, *shotahara*, and *sravahara*, it may perform *Sampraptivighatana* in *Vataja Pratishyaya*. *Nasya* performs the role of *dosha pratyani-Kachikitsa* with *Pathadi taila*. *Nasya's* most likely mode of action the drug is administered by the nose, enters the bloodstream through the nasal vein accumulate in the ocular and face veins. Communicates with the cavernous sinus, particularly when the head is dropped owing to gravity. The drug's active ingredient is absorbed and regulates circulatory and neurological processes demonstrating a systemic impact. The following is an explanation of *Pathadi Taila Nasya's* mode of action: *Pathadi Taila* has a high ability to spread through little channels because of this. *Tikshnata & Ushnata* of *Pathaadi Taila* are most likely the cause of *Avarana bhedana*. *Srothoshodan* is made up of *Tikta -Katu Rasa*, *Laghu -Tikshna Guna*, *Ushna -Veerya*, and *Katu -Vipaka*. The majority of the substances have anti-inflammatory properties that also stop inflammation. The *Taila's Kapha-Vata doshghnata* causes the symptoms to subside. By blocking the inflammatory action of leucocytes in the nose and preventing the production of inflammatory mediators from mast cells and basophils, *Pathaadi Taila* has an anti-inflammatory effect on the nasal mucosa. It is concluded that *Sashtriya Ayurvedic* drugs, such as *Pathadi Taila for Nasya*, are more helpful in managing *Pratishyaya* since this study produced substantial results across all assessment criteria.

7. CONCLUSION

According to its many *Siddhant*, *Ayurveda* provides extremely promising therapy options for these *vataja pratishayaya*. However, almost every symptom of *Vataja Pratishyaya*, including sneezing, nasal discharge, nasal obstruction, and nasal itching, is comparable to allergic rhinitis. It may thus be connected to *vataja Pratishyaya* within 28 days, *Shirogata Sthanik Snehana* and *Swedana*, followed by *Pathadi Taila Nasya*, provided a satisfying result in the current study.

8. REFERENCES

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